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STEAM education in schools and its benefits
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Annatation: This article discusses the benefits and importance of the STEAM program, helping students learn lessons better with the help of various international programs.

Key words: STEAM, science, education system, learning, academic performance.

Today's children are very smart and intelligent. They are growing up in line with the technologies of the new era. It is the need of the hour to make them interested in learning and to search for new methodological ways of imparting knowledge. We can see an unconventional way of teaching now. In it, children do not study dozens of subjects and textbooks as a special subject. This is the STEAM education system. What is the STEAM educational system? If we expand this abbreviation, we get the following: STEAM is S - science, T - technology, E - engineering, A - art and M - math. In English it goes like this: science, technology, engineering, art and mathematics. Do not forget that these directions are becoming the most popular in the modern world. Therefore, today the STEAM system is developing as one of the main trends. STEAM education is based on the application of a practical approach and the integration of all five areas into a single educational system. How the STEAM approach affects academic performance is that practice is just as important as theory. That is, during learning, we should work not only with our brain, but also with our hands. Learning only in the classroom is not keeping pace with the rapidly changing world. The main difference of the STEAM approach is that children use both their brains and their hands to successfully learn different subjects. They "learn" the knowledge they have received. In a STEAM learning environment, children acquire knowledge and learn to use it immediately. Therefore, when they grow up and face life's problems, whether it is environmental pollution or global climate change, they understand that such complex issues can only be solved by relying on knowledge from different fields and working together. It is not enough to rely on knowledge of this topic. By focusing on practical skills, students develop their will, creativity, flexibility and learn to cooperate with others. These skills and knowledge constitute the main task of education, that is, what

the educational system strives for. This new approach to education is the logical result of combining all theory and practice. Involvement of children in STEAM, this education should start from preschool age, therefore, it is necessary to include programs in kindergarten. Through the STEAM education system, creativity, curiosity, curiosity and the most important feature - the ability to solve problems are formed in the child. . "STEAM thinking" starts from childhood. In conclusion, it can be said that STEAM is a method of teaching natural sciences, technologies, engineering, arts and mathematics in harmony. Unlike education, STEAM technology ensures that knowledge is not isolated, but mutually proportional. Children develop the skills of non-standard thinking, finding multiple solutions to problems, and creativity, which will be very useful in their future work. This shows that STEAM technologies have a great place for the young generation today. It is recommended to use STEAM technologies in educational processes, taking into account the popularity of STEAM technologies today, their effectiveness and advantages in education. The gradual transformation of how everything is managed by new, innovative technologies and the Internet requires everyone to acquire skills such as critical thinking and problem solving, which are supported by STEM education.

Developing STEM students with enhanced cognitive strengths encourages students to think and find creative solutions to problems.

Over time, these students learn to think critically and refer to unbiased data and facts to support their arguments.

Being part of the STEM education system gives you the opportunity to ask questions like "why" and "how".

You are encouraged to explore your imagination and this ensures that a stream of exciting possibilities are open to you.

When students are interested, they are more eager to experience and learn, and invest time and effort in their education. Scientific theories and problems can be too complex and time-consuming to tackle alone.

Not surprisingly, STEM education systems emphasize the importance of collaboration and teamwork.

At work and in research institutions, the enormity and complexity of a project requires people to work in teams and develop solutions.

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Through STEM, students learn that demonstrating leadership and communication skills is more effective in achieving common goals more quickly.

When they are exposed to a team-oriented environment, children learn how to work with their peers, preparing them for future careers and networking at networking events. As children enter educational institutions, STEM fields help develop languages.

Opening doors to discussion and acquiring new vocabulary improves students' general knowledge and language.

Over time, these people are better equipped to step outside their comfort zone.

Also, interacting with people from other cultures and countries, helping them grow and embrace an open, diverse worldview.

STEM students succeed in their careers because they are willing to learn and are equipped with the resources gained over time to help them achieve their goals.

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